

The Impact of Interactive Puzzle Game Media on Junior High School Students' Explanatory Text Writing Ability: A Study in Indonesia

Edy Suprayetno¹, Cempaka Putri²

^{1,2}Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of interactive learning media based on puzzle games on the ability to write explanatory texts. The study population was all 8th grade students totaling 188. The research sample was 31 students of class VIII-C. The research method used a quantitative method. The research instrument used was an experiment with a one-group pretest-posttest design. Based on the research results, the ability to write explanatory texts before using the puzzle game media, the average score was 53.87, which was considered insufficient. 4 students (12.90%) obtained the good category, 12 students (38.70%) obtained the sufficient category, 6 students (19.35%) obtained the poor category, and 9 students (29.03%) obtained the very poor category. The ability to write explanatory text after using puzzle game media has an average of 72.41 which is considered good. 7 students (22.58%) received the very good category, 20 students (64.51%) received the good category, 3 students (9.67%) received the sufficient category, and 1 student (3.2%) received the very poor category. The results of this study found that there was a significant influence on the use of interactive puzzle game media to improve the ability to write explanatory text in grade VIII students of SMP Negeri 37 Medan, Indonesia.

KEYWORDS: Interactive Media, Puzzle Games, Writing Skills, Explanatory Text

1. INTRODUCTION

In the current millennial era, technology has become a primary focus in learning. According to Sadikin and Hakim (2019), technological advances can help students easily access a wide range of information. Therefore, teachers need to master, innovate, and utilize technological developments in the learning process. The use of interactive and creative learning media plays a crucial role in improving the quality of the teaching and learning process. Engaging media can foster student interest and motivation to be more active in learning because the material is presented in a more varied, easy-to-understand, and engaging manner. For teachers, learning media also serves as a tool that helps explain material more effectively, systematically, and communicatively. Furthermore, the presence of technology in learning provides many conveniences for both teachers and students, as it allows for a more flexible learning process without being limited by space and time. With technology, learning activities can take place not only during school hours but also outside of class hours through various digital platforms that support interaction, discussion, and continuous access to materials. Therefore, the use of technology-based interactive media greatly supports the creation of more effective, efficient learning, and is in accordance with the needs of modern educational development (Putra and Fatmasari, 2019).

Game-assisted learning is an innovation that can meet various basic needs to support a more effective and engaging teaching and learning process. Through this game-assisted media, the management of learning materials can be carried out in a more structured manner, making it easier for teachers and students to access learning content. Furthermore, game-assisted learning also supports a constructive learning process because students do not only receive information passively but also actively engage in understanding the material. Learning materials can be presented interactively in various forms, such as text, images, or other visual activities that can increase learning appeal. The material download feature also makes it easy for students to review the material at any time as needed. In addition, this learning supports the inquiry process through a material search facility that allows students to find information independently. The existence of discussion forums also expands opportunities for students to exchange opinions, ask questions, and build shared understanding. From an evaluation perspective, game-assisted learning makes it easier for teachers to assess student learning outcomes in a more practical and measurable manner. In fact, the material can be developed into fragments of images, photos, or text, making learning more varied, creative, and tailored to the needs of students (Tambunan, 2013).

Similarly, Murdiyani (2012) expressed that learning materials packaged on websites provide students with more flexible access to learning resources without being constrained by time and space. Through websites, students can study materials anytime and anywhere, according to their needs and readiness. This allows the learning process to take place not only in the classroom but also

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independently outside of school hours. Furthermore, learning websites allow for a more engaging and structured presentation of materials, whether in the form of text, images, videos, or practice questions, which can help students understand the material better. For teachers, using websites also makes it easier to provide learning materials that can be accessed repeatedly by students. Thus, packaging learning materials on websites significantly supports the creation of independent learning, increases learning accessibility, and adapts the educational process to increasingly advanced technological developments.

Interactive media in learning plays a crucial role in the teaching and learning process because it serves as a means to convey material more effectively to students. According to Hamid (2009), learning media is a component of a delivery strategy that contains the message or information to be conveyed to students. This media can be people, tools, or materials used to support the achievement of learning objectives. With learning media, the process of delivering material becomes clearer, more engaging, and easier for students to understand. Therefore, the use of learning media is essential to create more effective, interactive, and meaningful learning activities.

Likewise, according to Weda (2013), learning media is a component of a delivery strategy that can be loaded with messages delivered to students, whether in the form of people, tools, or materials. The use of interactive learning media has great benefits in the learning environment, both in delivering learning materials and in the efficiency of the time required. Yanto (2019) interactive learning media is one answer to the problem of abstract learning materials, packaging interactive learning media in the form of computer or mobile software and by adding good animation displays will attract students' desire to learn and understand abstract learning concepts. In addition, interactive learning media is a form of affective learning media with the development of technology that demands learning in the 21st century.

Educational games are gaining popularity in the world of education because they are considered capable of adapting the learning process to developments in digital technology. This situation encourages educators to utilize game design elements as part of the learning strategies implemented in the curriculum. Through educational games, students can learn more actively because they not only receive material but also can see, hear, observe, and interact directly with the learning content through various buttons, tools, and navigation features. This interaction makes the learning process more interesting, enjoyable, and less monotonous. Furthermore, educational games also help students understand concepts more concretely through visual and participatory learning experiences. Amanda and Rianto (2018) explain that educational games are play media specifically designed to provide specific learning, develop students' concepts and understanding, train skills, and increase learning motivation. Thus, educational games can be an innovative, effective, and relevant learning medium to meet the needs of today's students.

Among the various types of interactive learning media, game-based learning media has added value because it can combine entertainment and education elements in one engaging activity. Essentially, games are a popular form of entertainment for children, so when used as a learning medium, students tend to feel happier, more enthusiastic, and more motivated in participating in the learning process. This allows students to learn while playing without feeling overwhelmed by the material presented. According to Tianti (2019), the use of games in learning can create a more enjoyable and effective learning experience. Furthermore, the implementation of games such as arranging images into puzzles can also make teaching and learning activities more innovative and varied. These activities not only train students' concentration, accuracy, and thinking skills but also reduce monotony in the learning atmosphere. Thus, game-based learning media can be an effective alternative for creating an active, creative, and enjoyable learning atmosphere.

Based on the description that has been presented, this study aims to analyze the impact of the use of interactive puzzle games media on the ability to write explanatory texts of students at State Junior High School 37, Medan City, Indonesia. This study was conducted to determine the extent to which interactive puzzle games media can help students understand the structure, content, and linguistic rules of explanatory texts more easily and interestingly in the process of learning to write explanatory texts for students. m

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a quantitative research with an experimental approach. One Group Pretest-Posttest Design type, namely research by giving an initial test (Pretest) before being given treatment, after being given treatment then giving a final test (Posttest). Quantitative experiments *One Group Pretest-Posttest Design* including pre-experimental design, also called simple quasi-experiments because they do not involve strong controls (Sugiyono). Table 1 is research design one group pretest-posttest design.

Table 1 Research Design One Group Pretest-Posttest Design

<i>st</i>	reatment	<i>Posttest</i>
O ₁	X	O ₂

The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling, which involves selecting a sample based on specific considerations. The sample consisted of one class chosen because it had characteristics consistent with the research objectives, thus

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employing a One Group Pretest–Posttest design. The sample of this research was class VIII students of State Junior High School 37 Medan, namely class VIII-C, totaling 31 students.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 RESULTS

The Ability to Write Explanatory Texts Before and After Using Puzzle Game Media

Based on the data from the test results of the ability to write explanatory texts before using the puzzle game media, the highest score was 75 and the lowest score was 15 with a total of 1,670 data and an average score of 53.87. The basis for calculating the mean and standard deviation of the values is as follows: The pretest of students' explanatory text writing skills is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Frequency Distribution of Calculating Mean and Standard Pretest

No.	X	F	FX	X - \bar{X}	X ²	FX ²
1.	15	1	15	-38.8	1,505.44	1,505.44
2.	30	1	30	-23.8	566.44	566.44
3.	35	1	35	-18.8	353.44	353.44
4.	40	2	80	-13.8	190.44	380.88
5.	45	4	180	-8.8	77.44	309.76
6.	50	6	300	-3.8	14.44	86.64
7.	60	7	420	6.1	37.21	260.47
8.	65	5	325	11.1	123.21	616.05
9.	70	3	210	16.1	259.21	777.63
10.	75	1	75	21.1	445.21	445.21
Total		31	1,670			2,539.44

Meanwhile, the data display in the form of a percentage (%) of the level of ability to write explanatory text before using puzzle game media is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Percentage (%) of Ability to Write Explanatory Text Before Using Puzzle Game Media

Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Category
80-100	-	0%	Very good
66-79	4	12.90%	Good
56-65	12	38.70%	Enough
46-55	6	19.35%	Not enough
0-45	9	29.03%	Very less

Based on Table 3 above, it is explained that the percentage of the level of ability to write explanatory text before using puzzle game media is 4 students (12.90%) in the good category, 12 students (38.70%) in the sufficient category, and 6 students (19.35%) in the less category, and 9 students (29.03%) in the very less category.

Furthermore, the ability to write explanatory text using puzzle game media has the highest score of 95, while the lowest score is 40 with a total score of 2,250, and an average score of 72.58. Data presentation in the form of frequency distribution, mean score and posttest standard as in Table 4.

Table 4 Frequency Distribution, Mean and Standard

No.	X	F	FX	X - \bar{X}	X ²	FX ²
1.	40	1	40	-32.5	1,056.25	1,056.25
2.	60	2	120	-12.5	156.25	312.5
3.	65	1	65	-7.5	56.25	56.25
4.	70	13	910	-2.5	6.25	81.25
5.	75	5	525	2.4	5.76	40.32
6.	80	5	400	7.4	54.76	273.8
7.	90	1	90	17.4	302.76	302.76
8.	95	1	95	22.4	501.76	501.76
Total		31	2,245			2,624.89

Meanwhile, the data display in the form of a percentage (%) of the level of ability to write explanatory text after using puzzle game media is presented in Table 5.

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Table 5 Percentage (%) of Ability to Write Explanatory Text After Using Puzzle Game Media

Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Category
80-100	7	22.58	Very good
66-79	20	64.51	Good
56-65	3	9.67	Enough
46-55	-	-	Not enough
0-45	1	3.2	Very less

Based on Table 5 above, the percentage of the ranking of the ability to write explanatory text after using puzzle game media is 7 students (22.58%) in the very good category, 20 students (64.51%) in the good category, 3 students (9.67%) in the sufficient category, and 1 student (3.2%) in the very poor category.

The Impact of Puzzle Games Media on Writing Skills

Explanatory Text

Based on the data analysis presented in Table 6 below, it can be concluded that learning using puzzle games has a positive impact on the explanatory text writing skills of students at public junior high schools in Medan City, Indonesia. This is indicated by an increase in students' writing scores between before and after the treatment.

Table 6 Summary of Difference Test Before and After the Ability to Write Explanatory Text Using Puzzle Game Media

No.	Element	Before	After
1.	Total Value	1,670	2,250
2.	Average (Mean)	53.87	72.41
3.	Standard Deviation	9.05	9.20

The improvement in students' ability to write explanatory texts indicates that the use of puzzle games can help them understand the structure and linguistic rules of explanatory texts more effectively. Furthermore, the interactive, game-based nature of the media also increases student engagement and motivation during the learning process.

Thus, interactive puzzle games serve not only as a learning aid but also as an innovative strategy that can create a more engaging, enjoyable, and meaningful learning environment. The implications of these findings suggest that integrating interactive learning media into Indonesian language learning has the potential to improve student learning outcomes, particularly in explanatory text writing skills.

4. DISCUSSION

The value of the ability to write explanatory text before using puzzle game media has an average of 53.87 which is said to be less. Students who obtained (12.90%) in the good category were 4 students, students who obtained (38.70%) in the sufficient category were 12 students, students who obtained (19.35%) in the less category were 6 students, and students who obtained (29.03%) in the very less category were 9 students. Meanwhile, the value of the ability to write explanatory text after using puzzle game media had an average of 72.41 which was said to be good. Students who obtained (22.58%) in the very good category were 7 students, students who obtained (64.51%) in the good category were 20 students, students who obtained (9.67%) in the sufficient category were 3 students, and students who obtained (3.2%) in the very less category were 1 student.

There is an impact on the ability to write explanatory text with interactive puzzle game media. Based on the t-test, the calculated t value is $> t$ table, namely $8.46 > 1.67$, thus the hypothesis is accepted. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant impact of interactive puzzle game media on improving the ability to write explanatory texts of students at State Junior High School 37 Medan, Indonesia.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the data analysis obtained from the research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The ability to write explanatory text before using puzzle game media had an average of 53.87 which was said to be lacking. 4 students obtained (12.90%) in the good category, 12 students obtained (38.70%) in the sufficient category, 6 students obtained (19.35%) in the less category, and 9 students obtained (29.03%) in the very less category.
2. The ability to write explanatory text after using puzzle game media had an average of 72.41 which is said to be good. Students who obtained (22.58%) in the very good category were 7 students, 20 students obtained (64.51%) in the good category, 3 students obtained (9.67%) in the sufficient category, and 1 student obtained (3.2%) in the very poor category.

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3. Based on the t-test, the calculated t-value is $8.46 > 1.67$, meaning the hypothesis is accepted. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant influence of puzzle game media on improving the ability to write explanatory texts.

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